

Oxidation of Sulphur Dioxide and Hydrogen Sulphide by Sodium Perborate

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Oxidation of sulphur dioxide by sodium perborate yields sulphate, whereas that of hydrogen sulphide leads to a complicated reaction with the formation of sulphate, sulphite, thiosulphate, and dithionate. Simultaneous interaction of various intermediate products themselves and their oxidation continue throughout. To avoid decomposition of perborate, the medium of reaction has always been maintained alkaline.

In continuation with the earlier study of oxidation of sulphur dioxide¹, selenium dioxide², and hydrogen sulphide³ with different oxidising substances, sodium perborate has been selected for the present investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium perborate of A. R. quality was used. Aqueous solutions of sulphur dioxide (normal) and hydrogen sulphide (saturated at 0°) were freshly prepared, when required, as before.

Reaction with Sulphur Dioxide.—To sodium perborate of A.R. quality (1 g.), suspended in about 15 ml of ice-cold distilled water containing excess of sodium bicarbonate, freshly prepared sulphurous acid (normal, 25 ml) was added slowly. The resulting solution was found to be free from any perborate and showed the presence of sulphate and unchanged sulphite ions. The former was estimated as barium sulphate⁴ after stabilising the latter with glycerol.

The experiment was repeated with 20, 15, and 10 ml of normal sulphurous acid in a similar way. In the first experiment, some unchanged sulphite and in the remaining experiments, some unchanged perborate were detected. Sulphate was estimated as before.

Reduction with Hydrogen Sulphide.—To sodium perborate (1 g.), suspended in water, freshly prepared hydrogen sulphide water (30 ml) was added similarly. A yellow colour due to formation of polysulphides, as an intermediate product and disappearing slowly after the additions of hydrogen sulphide water, was noticed. The reaction mixture showed

1. Lal *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 65–547; 1956, **33**, 668; 1957, **34**, 131; 1960, **37**, 181; *Res. Bull. Panj. Univ.*, 1959, **10**, 257.
2. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 467; 1961, **38**, 57; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, **19B**, 162.
3. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1952, **29**, 934; 1955, **32**, 58.
4. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", p. 401, 1960, Longmans Green & Co. Ltd., London.

absence of perborate. Since polysulphides were present in excess, the simultaneous existence of thionates with more than two sulphur atoms in the same solution was not possible⁵.

TABLE I
Oxidation of N-H₂SO₃ by sodium perborate.

NaBO₃·4H₂O taken = 1.0 g.

Expt. No.	N-H ₂ SO ₃ added.	NaBO ₃ ·4H ₂ O recovered unchanged.	SO ₄ ²⁻ .	H ₂ SO ₃ recovered unchanged.
1	10.0 ml	Yes	0.4100 g. 0.4310	No
2	15.0	Yes	0.6180 0.6200	No
3	20.0	No	0.6430 0.6400	yes
4	25.0	No	0.6419 0.6415	Yes

TABLE II
Oxidation of hydrogen sulphide by sodium perborate.

NaBO₃·4H₂O taken = 1.0 g.

Exp. No.	H ₂ S water added.	Recovered unchanged. NaBO ₃ ·4H ₂ O. H ₂ S.		SO ₄ ²⁻ .	S ₂ O ₆ ²⁻ .	S ₂ O ₅ ²⁻ .	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ .
1	5.0ml	Yes	No.	0.0543 g. 0.0535	0.0049 g. 0.0052	Nil	Nil
2	10.0	Yes	No.	0.0916 .0910	0.0126 0.0122	„	„
3	20.0	No	No.	0.0825 0.0815	0.0392 0.0395	0.0531 g. 0.0518	„ „
4	30.0	No	Yes	0.0258 0.0249	0.0210 0.0212	0.1089 0.1096	0.0312 g. 0.0305

Some glycerol was added and any unchanged hydrogen sulphide and the polysulphides were eliminated with aqueous suspension of cadmium carbonate. The resulting filtrate was made to a known volume and analysed as follows:

(i). In an aliquot, formalin was added to inactivate any sulphite and thiosulphate was estimated iodimetrically⁶.

(ii). In another aliquot, both sulphite and thiosulphate were estimated together iodimetrically and their values were determined⁶.

5. Kolthoff and Belcher, "Volumetric Analysis", Vol. 3, p. 299, 1957, Interscience Publishers Inc., New York.

6. *Idem, ibid.*, p. 300.

(iii). In a third aliquot, all the sulphur compounds except dithionate were destroyed with alkaline permanganate solution and dithionate, which remained unattacked, was estimated by Murthy's method⁷.

(iv). In a similar aliquot, sulphite was inactivated as above, thiosulphate was converted to tetrathionate by adding the above determined volume of iodine solution in acetic acid medium, and the sulphate content was estimated as barium sulphate⁸.

When 20 ml of hydrogen sulphide water was used, the yellow colour, produced during the addition, disappeared after some time. Both, perborate and hydrogen sulphide (or polysulphides), were found to be absent. Sulphate, dithionate, and thiosulphate were estimated as before. Sulphite was found to be absent as the titre values of the iodine solution before and after the addition of formalin were the same. To detect the presence of higher thionates (tri, tetra, etc.), if any, thiosulphate present in a known portion of the solution was converted to tetrathionate by adding the above determined volume of the iodine solution: the higher thionates were converted to thiosulphate by heating with excess of sodium sulphide, the unchanged excess of which was removed by cadmium carbonate suspension in water, and the resulting thiosulphate was estimated iodimetrically in acetic acid medium. A blank titration under similar conditions was also performed and after making an allowance for this titration, it was found that the titre values required for thiosulphate alone and for total thiosulphate obtained after the sodium sulphide treatment were the same⁹. This indicated that no higher thionate was present in the reaction mixture.

The experiment was repeated with 10 and 5 ml of hydrogen sulphide water respectively. In each experiment, only unchanged perborate, sulphate, and dithionate were detected. After the automatic decomposition of perborate present in the reaction mixture, both sulphate and dithionate were estimated. Formation of any higher thionate was not detected in any of these experiments also.

TABLE III

Oxidation of potassium tetrathionate by sodium perborate.

Tetrathionate solution used = 1% (aqueous). Perborate taken = 1.0 g.

Sr. No.	K ₂ S ₄ O ₆ soln. added.	Unchanged K ₂ S ₄ O ₆ .	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ formed.	S ₂ O ₆ ²⁻ formed. (g)	SO ₄ ²⁻ formed.
1	5 ml	Nil	0.0023 g. 0.0023	0.0060 g. 0.0060	0.0527g. 0.0531
2	10	..	0.0046 0.0039	0.0240 0.0249	0.0926 0.0932
3	20	..	0.0060 0.0060	0.0801 0.0807	0.1531 0.1523
4	30	..	0.0075 0.0075	0.1563 0.1575	0.1814 0.1810

7. Murthy, *Curr. Sci.*, 1953, 22, 371; Kolthoff and Belcher, "Volumetric Analysis", Vol. 3, p. 302.

8. Sutton, "Systematic Handbook of Volumetric Analysis", p. 431, 1955, J. & A. Churchill Ltd., London.

9. Kolthoff and Belcher, "Volumetric Analysis", Vol. 3, p. 301, 1957.

TABLE IV

Oxidation of sodium thiosulphate by sodium perborate.
Thiosulphate solution used = 2%. Perborate taken = 1.0 g.

Sr. No.	$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ soln. added.	Unchanged $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$.	SO_4^{2-} formed.	$\text{S}_2\text{O}_6^{2-}$ formed.
1	10 ml	Nil	0.1234 g. 0.1226	0.0281 g. 0.0271
2	20	..	0.2235 0.2215	0.07131 0.0758
3	30	0.0143 g. 0.0108	0.2520 0.2536	0.1640 0.1622

DISCUSSION

It appears that in the first part of the reaction, there is a simple one-stage oxidation of sulphite to sulphate, perborate being reduced to borate. No intermediate products, whatsoever, are therefore suspected. The reaction may be represented as :

But the reaction with hydrogen sulphide is not unambiguous and it provides sulphate, dithionate, thiosulphate, and sulphite. So long as the perborate is not completely acted upon, sulphate and dithionate are the only products (Table II, expt. 1 and 2). Afterwards thiosulphate also appears among the products of reaction; dithionate increases and sulphate decreases. A further increase in hydrogen sulphide water produces sulphite also; thiosulphate increases and both sulphate and dithionate decrease (Table II, expt. 4).

Appearance of the yellow colour suggests that polysulphides are probably the primary products of the reaction as:

But the subsequent disappearance of the yellow colour with the formation of other sulphur compounds suggests that polysulphides undergo further oxidation through quite a complicated course of reaction. Sulphur, which is the primary product of oxidation of these polysulphides as:

leads to the formation of sulphite in alkaline medium. The medium being alkaline and both sulphur and oxygen available, the reaction proceeds further with a probable mechanism represented as:

It is evident from the above suggested mechanism in alkaline medium that thiosulphate is oxidised to tetrathionate which is further oxidised to dithionate and sulphate. The analytical results show that the formation of dithionate reaches its maximum and that of thiosulphate just appears when the perborate is completely acted upon, whereas tetrathionate has not been detected at any stage of the reaction at all. This suggests that further formation of thiosulphate in the reaction is effected only when tetrathionate resulting from its oxidation is oxidised to dithionate and sulphate completely. This chain of reactions continues till whole of the perborate is reduced. A decrease in sulphate and dithionate, an increase in thiosulphate, and appearance of sulphite among the products of reaction in the final experiment (Table II, expt. 4) indicate that in presence of excess of hydrogen sulphide, the reaction tends to remain in its early stages rather than proceeding to the higher oxidation products.

With a view to establishing the formation of dithionate from the oxidation of thiosulphate *via* tetrathionate, as suggested by the above proposed mechanism, the reactions of tetrathionate and thiosulphate with perborate have been studied independently.

Oxidation of tetrathionate by perborate produces mainly sulphate and dithionate with a very small amount of thiosulphate (Table III). Formation of sulphate and dithionate provides an adequate evidence in favour of the above mechanism and also explains the formation of sulphate and dithionate, obtained in the oxidation of thiosulphate by perborate (Table IV). Formation of some thiosulphate may be regarded to be due to a side reaction of tetrathionate in an alkaline medium¹⁰ as:

The amount of sulphite thus resulting is extremely small and is probably oxidised forthwith to sulphate in absence of free sulphur.

Absence of tetrathionate and presence of a very small amount of thiosulphate in the reaction mixture further show that oxidation of tetrathionate to sulphate and dithionate is faster than the actual formation of tetrathionate. It is probably due to this reason that tetrathionate is not detected at any stage of the reaction (Table II), whereas thiosulphate has been detected in certain experiments (expt. 3 and 4, Table II). But the amount of dithionate is much smaller than that expected in accordance to the above mechanism. Higher values of sulphate, however, suggest a probability of its further oxidation as:

Possibility of sulphate formation due to one-stage oxidation of sulphite as:

appears to have very remote chances because it would lead to a regular increase in the sulphate content, which is contrary to the experimental data. So long as free sulphur is present in the reaction mixture, sulphite is converted into thiosulphate, but later on, when no free sulphur is available and perborate is still present, any sulphite would be

10. Chapin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 625.

oxidised to sulphate. Also, when both free sulphur and perborate are absent, sulphite would appear as one of the reaction products (Table II, expt. 4).

Bassett and Henery¹¹ have shown the formation of dithionate in acidic medium as:

But in the present investigation, when the medium is alkaline, it may conclusively be due to the oxidation of thiosulphate, one of the intermediate products, through tetrathionate formation and not the sulphite. This fact is well supported by the results obtained in the oxidation of sulphurous acid by perborate where although the sulphite ions are introduced in excess, due to absence of free sulphur, no thiosulphate and subsequent dithionate formation have been detected at all.

Formation of dithionate in alkaline medium, according to the mechanism proposed above, has also been confirmed by the oxidation of thiosulphate by perborate, where only dithionate and sulphate are the end products (Table IV).

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